

Weekly Progress Report

Date: 26/10/2015 – 30/10/2015

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Emmanuel Kondela

Mary Nsabagwa

Plans:

- Finish and send Revision 3 of the Bergen Evaluation Report
- Discussions and selection of student groups at ECE department at Makerere to work with Max on power-related design for the EA prototype

Activities:

- Version 3 of the evaluation report has been compiled and will be available in 1-2 days. Its structure has been overhauled to look like the suggested structure that was given in the feedback to version 2.
- Student groups at the ECE department at Makerere were asked to submit interest to 4 AWS related projects. The projects will be supervised by Maximus Byamukama and Richard Okou.
- The WIMEA ICT poster contents were discussed by the whole WIMEA student team, finished and sent to Maxwell Omwega for graphics design. The poster will be entitled “Seeing Business in Weather”

Plans for next week

- Work on PhD proposals and generate paper ideas and we await feedback to version 3
- Mary and Emmanuel to look for topics where students at their respective departments can help
- Begin a systems analysis for the open source version of the RS firmware and assign tasks